

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B437
 Date: 23 Apr 2009
 Take Off: 03:22:00Z
 Landing: 07:56:20Z
 Flight Time 4h 34m 20s

Campaign: MEVEX Dust Flight 2
Operating Area: Oman

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsey-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Pollard	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM	
6	Core Chem / AVAPS	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM	
8	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office	
10	Wet Neph / CVI / IIR	Andy Wilson	Met Office	
11	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office	
12	Mission Scientist 2	Dave Kindred	Met Office	
13	Mission Scientist 3	John Marsham	NCAS Leeds	
14	Filters	Anne Klaver	University of Paris	
15	Mini-LIDAR	Joss Kent	Met Office	
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
CVI	No log passed to FAAM yet
SWS	No log passed to FAAM yet
IIR	No IIR log is provided for the Flight Folder

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	03 Nov 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090423_r0_b437_035652_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090423_r0_b437_045652_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090423_r0_b437_063204_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090423_r0_b437_073204_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090423_r0_b437_035647_1hz.avi
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 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090423_r0_b437_063159_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090423_r0_b437_073159_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20090423_r0_b437_035821_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090423_r0_b437_045821_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090423_r0_b437_063208_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090423_r0_b437_073208_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20090423_r0_b437_ir035821_1hz.avi
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17				
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19				

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PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Filters	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
CVI	No log passed to FAAM yet
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faam-video-ffc_faam_20090423_r0_b437_035643_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090423_r0_b437_045643_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090423_r0_b437_063156_1hz.avi
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FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B437
 Date: 23rd April 2009
 Project: MEVEX
 Location: Oman

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
030906		Start-Up	0.10 kft	001	
031314		!	0.09 kft	001	start taxi
031335		!	0.09 kft	036	ASPs opened
031533		!	0.08 kft	018	start pirouette
031846		!	0.08 kft	072	end pirouette
032200		T/O	3.5 kft	071	Muscat
032639		!	7.1 kft	071	Nevzorov/JW zero
032853		!	7.1 kft	071	Heimann cal
033012		!	8.9 kft	071	GIN reset
034202		!	21.0 kft	116	GIN ok
034909	041506	Profile 1	20.9 - 0.27 kft	195	QNH 1013
035020		!	20.0 kft	194	NEv/JW zero
035604		!	14.1 kft	194	GE error
041512	042140	Run 1	0.26 kft	193	run at 250ft
041620		!	0.25 kft	191	Heimann cal
041632		!	0.26 kft	191	Nevzorov/JW zero
042231	042356	Orbit 1	0.56 - 0.55 kft	162	
042713	042811	Profile 2	0.44 - 0.12 kft	335	
042811	043953	Run 2	0.12 - 0.15 kft	334	
042834		!	0.12 kft	335	Heimann cal
044134	045510	Run 3	1.5 kft	329	
044400		!	1.5 kft	329	Heimann cal
044546		!	1.5 kft	330	Nevzorov/JW zero
045635	051923	Profile 3	1.5 - 24.0 kft	171	
052530	054700	Run 4	24.0 kft	169	054355
052530		Sonde 1	24.0 kft	329	
053145		Sonde 2	24.0 kft	327	
053258		Sonde 3	24.0 kft	327	
053759		Sonde 4	24.0 kft	327	
054700		Sonde 5	24.0 kft	169	at end run
054807	060553	Run 5	24.1 - 24.0 kft	119	
060106		!	24.0 kft	161	TWC evap 2 switched on
060619	060754	Orbit 2	24.0 kft	144	abandoned
060818	061101	Orbit 3	24.1 - 24.0 kft	350	
061350	062538	Profile 4	24.0 - 12.1 kft	312	
062549	063643	Run 6	12.0 kft	328	
063832	064555	Profile 5	12.1 - 5.0 kft	139	
064602	064922	Profile 6	5.0 - 8.0 kft	157	
065254	070624	Run 7	8.0 kft	328	

065824	!	8.0 kft	326 JW/Nevzorov zero	
070811	071641	Profile 7	8.0 - 1.5 kft	153
071001	!	6.3 kft	150 TWC evap 2 off	
071801	072658	Run 8	1.5 kft	003 QNH1013
075620	Land	0.09 kft	207 Muscat	
075910	!	0.09 kft	258 start pirouette	
080218	!	0.09 kft	110 end pirouette	
080925	Shutdown	0.09 kft	267 23 35.36N 58 17.66E	

B437 01:33:32-08:17:04

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

OOMS -> OOMA - Overview

NavData Cycle 2009-4 Expires: Thursday, 07 May 2009.

Scale: 1:1465551 (1 inch = 20.10 naut mi). Printed on 22 Apr 2009

7 6 9 9 6 ; 6 8

FliteStar 9.4.5.0

MEVEX – Aerosol and Land Surface Emissivity Sortie – B437**Date: 23rd April 2009****Mission Scientist:****T/O OOMS: 03:30Z (07:30 local)****Land OOMS: 07:30Z (11:30 local)****Location:** West coast of Oman and Ramlat Al Wahibah – Oman Low Level Flying Area 1. Point A: 20°30'N 59°30'E Point B: 22°00'N 58°40'E**Weather:** Cloud free conditions low aerosol loadings**Sortie Aim:** To validate forecasts of moderate aerosol conditions and the IR and microwave surface emissivity of desert surfaces coordinated with an IASI overpass.**Key Instruments:** ARIES, MARSS, SWS/SHIMS, IR Cameras, Mini Lidar, Small particulate probes, SID 3, AVAPS, Nephs**Sortie profile:**

Item No.	Detail	Item time	Running time	Local time
1	Take off OOMS		03:30:00	07:30:00
2	Transit to KAXEM at FL210	00:25:00	03:55:00	07:55:00
3	Profile descent to 100 ft at 1000 ft/min reducing to 500 ft/min in boundary layer	00:20:00	04:15:00	08:15:00
4	Fly straight and level run at 100 ft to point A	00:10:00	04:25:00	08:25:00
5	Perform an orbit at bank angle to be determined by mission scientist	00:10:00	04:35:00	08:35:00
6	SLR at low level from A to B	00:25:00	05:00:00	09:00:00
7	Profile ascent to FL240 at 1000 ft/min to arrive at point A	00:25:00	05:25:00	09:25:00
8	2 x SLR at FL240 dropping 4 sondes during first run	00:50:00	06:15:00	10:15:00
9	Perform an orbit at bank angle to be determined by mission scientist	00:10:00	06:25:00	10:25:00
10	Profile descent to FL150 at 1000 ft/min	00:10:00	06:35:00	10:35:00
11	SLR at FL150 towards B	00:10:00	06:45:00	10:45:00
12	Profile descent to 5000 ft at 1000 ft/min	00:10:00	06:55:00	10:55:00
13	SLR at 5000 ft towards B	00:10:00	07:05:00	11:05:00
14	Recover to OOMS	00:25:00	07:30:00	11:30:00
	Total sortie time		04:00:00	04:00:00

Mission Scientist's Debrief – B437 MEVEX

23rd April 2009

David Pollard

Sortie Aim:

The aim of this sortie was to characterise the atmospheric column and its radiative properties in conjunction with an IASI overpass with low aerosol loading conditions.

Weather:

Conditions in the operating area were stable with light/calm winds at the surface with a strengthening westerly component at higher levels. Aerosol loadings were lower than encountered during the previous flight and stably stratified.

Sortie overview:

Following a pirouette manoeuvre on the ground (solar zenith angle 65.9°) the take off was followed by a non-profile climb to transit level, FL210, which showed a boundary layer up to ~FL020 as indicated by a hydrolapse, and caps in the concentrations of aerosol given by the nephelometers and PCASPs. The transit finished at waypoint KAXEM and was followed by a profile descent to the south to 250 ft slowing to 500 ft/min below 5000 ft. The profile encountered aerosol (PCASPs, Neph and O3) at FL140, which was consistent with the lidar soundings observed during transit. During this profile the lidar also showed that there was a clearance below the aerosol layer. The top of the marine boundary layer was found to be at ~750 ft, indicated by a strong hydrolapse. This was followed by a run at 250ft.

On reaching Point A ($20^\circ30'N$ $59^\circ30'E$) an 45° orbit was carried out at 500 ft (solar zenith angle 53°) followed by the remainder of the profile down to 100 ft, showing an increase in PCASP concentrations coincident with a drop in Nox. Just before reaching the coast, a dry dusty region was encountered, possibly the remnants of an overnight land breeze. On reaching the coast the aircraft climbed to 2000 ft before dropping to the new run height of 1500 ft.

At this point it was very obvious that there were two distinct dust layers the remainder of the run to Point B ($22^\circ00'N$ $58^\circ40'E$) seemed to be in the clear(ish) slot with low Neph scattering and PCASP concentrations around 100/cc. Towards the end of the run colder and moister air was encountered, indicating the convective boundary layer.

A profile was then performed from B to A, climbing to FL240 encountering a low concentration dusty/moist layer between 6000 and 14000 ft.

At FL240, two SLRs were performed between A and B dropping 5 sondes. The parachutes failed on sondes 2 and 3 and the winds on sonde 5 were noisy. This run was coincident with the IASI overpass at 05:44Z.

Back at point A an orbit was carried out (after one aborted attempt) at a bank angle of 30° (solar zenith angle $\sim 31^\circ$).

We then profiled down, towards B, to 1200ft, a level identified by the Lidar, sondes and previous profile as being at the top of the dust layer and continued with a run at this level to B during which the PCASPs showed concentrations of 200-300/cc.

Turning back towards A a profile was carried out down to 5000 ft, out of the dust layer, before returning to 8000 ft for a run back to B in the bottom of the dust layer.

On reaching B, it was decided to use some extra time on task available to us to profile down to, and carry out a short run in, the lowest dust layer. Concentrations in this layer were fairly light, ~ 100 /cc.

At the end of this run a recovery was made to Muscat, with a pirouette after landing (solar zenith angle $\sim 11^\circ$).

Summary:

This was a good IASI sortie with low aerosol loadings and otherwise clear skies over desert and sea with generally stable, stratified conditions although some small scale dynamic features were in evidence.

Mission Scientist's Log

192.168.101.161
: 1266

Flight No **B.437**... Date **23/4/9**..... Name **Pollard**..... Page **1** of **5**.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					No SID 3 due to comms failure pre-flight
3:13:20					off chals
03:15:33			045		Start of Pirouette
03:18:46					end of Pirouette
03:21:00			260		T/P
					Light aerosol coding P
					constrained to below mtn tops
					25 m/s 50 mph NBY O ₂
					2000 P _{CO2} FLOW BL by 20
					Hydrolyse 960 ml
					Clad Phys → COP 0 → max → 0
					FL good air 020
					Neph peak 126 to 130 @ 500 ft
03:49:01	P1	FL210	195	KAYEM	Start of profile
		FL140			P _{CO2} , Neph & O ₂ increasing consistently w/ lidar as descend
					Transit ~ FL130
04:00					P _{CO2} ^{old} 500 _{cu'} ^{new} 1000 _{cu'}
					CVI 200-250
04:01					dropping
04:02					deeper layer 2km below
04:03					" desupercooled
					Wet Neph not responding
04:05					Wet Neph back

Mission Scientist's Log350ft
50ft = mblFlight No **B.437** Date 23/4/9 Name Palmer Page 2 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
04:06		4300ft			interesting Lidar structure in prof
04:08					Very little contrast of horizon w/ these landing.
04:09					ish structure in Lidar
04:13:50					QNA 1013 SWS having comm problems w/ modules
					Neph peak = 3.54ft
					elevated O ₃ layer
4:15:00	P1/R1	250 100ft	195		strong hydrolysis in last 500ft of Prof. new PCASP back to sensible winds
4:21:40	R1	250ft			End
04:22:30	01	500ft	150		45° orbit left 52M 53°
04:23:56					end SWS 1 good orbit
04:27:15	P2	500ft	330	1A	to 100ft
04:28:11	P2/R2	100ft	330		1.572pph Max at 250ft down to 1 @ 100ft inc in PCASP conc
					Day near dusk towards sunset was not (no last) PCASP steady O ₃ inc

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.437** Date 23/4/9 Name Pollard Page 3 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
04:39:53	R2	100ft	330		Climb to 22ft Just before, encountered dry & dusty layer from overnight land breeze
04:41:34	R3				Very obvious double dust layer (photos)
04:44					Neph very low ~ 15-20 PCASP's ~ 100 cm^{-1}
04:49:45					Change in desert terrain
04:53:					entering convective BL (w/old heights)
04:53:12	R3	500ft		B	end
04:56:35	R3	500ft	170	B	profile to high level Neph and PCASP's increasing from about 6ft tying in w/ mist layer Neph & PCASP dropped right off as hit dew point
		1400ft			
05:19:23	^{R3} /R4	FL240		A	
05:25:30		"	330	A	Sonde 1 - good
05:31:45					Sonde 2 - 'chute fail'
05:32:58					" 3 " "
					Lidar showing layer 10ft below, consistent w/ profile up
05:37:59					Sonde 4 - good

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.437** Date 23/4/9 Name Adrian Page 4 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Lidar seeing layer top falling off slightly towards B
					@ coast low level layer
					? sea breeze lifting dust?
05:44:	R4				end and sonde 5
05:44:02	R5	FL240	120	B (uh)	
05:50					! Caution! wings <u>not</u> level
06:05:53	R5	"		A	
06:06:19	O2	"	140		Abandoned
06:08:19	O3		350		good
06:11:01	O3				end
06:13:50	R4	FL240	310	A	
		13800ft			turbulent
		13400ft			top of dust layer (w/m)
06:25:35	R4/R6	12000ft	320		in dust layer top
					Lidar seeing decrease below this layer (~2hft) and very low layer below
					PCASP old 2-300 cc ⁻¹ new noise
06:36:43	R6				end
06:38:32	R5	12000ft	140	B	
06:43:40					ANIES fails over
		6500ft			PCASP & Nephel drop off
06:45:55	R5/R6	5000ft			returning to 8hft for final run
06:46:02	R6	5000ft			"

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.347** Date 23/4/9 Name Palmer Page 5 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
06:49:22	R6	9hft			end
06:52:54	R7	9hft	320		Run in bottom of dust layer
					ARIES still inop
06:57					ARIES back
					leaving extra time to get bottom layer
07:06:24	R7	9hft			end of run
07:08:11	R7	8hft	150		↓ 1500ft
					PCASP / Neph concs dropping
					O ₃ increases
					300-100 ↓
		3hft			Concs increasing + dew point
					<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> hot probes: S103 no comms Wet Neph sometimes off PCASP (new) ARIES fell over SWS probes w/ comms to work </div>
07:16:01	R7				end in lower dust layer
07:18:01	R6	1500ft	N		Neph scab in 30's PCASP 100 cc ⁻¹
07:23					Lidar: dust thinning
07:26:56	R4	"			End of science

07:57:20
09:02:10

125
125

Pirouette

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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Flight No **B 437** Date 23 April 07 Name JOHN MARRAM Page 1 of 1

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
03:16	/	G	/	/	Pinnac - Much clearer since (letter us) than yesterday & day before (K436) Light winds.
03:18:42	/	G			Clear top of dusk BK scattered mtns End of Pinnac. P.
03:22:04		Talo - H.			P.P.P.P. - Out to Oz, Wx clear at 5960 mt
03:26					Coast Land → Sea → Land.
03:31:52					P.P.P mtns + sea
03:34:00					P.P.mtns + sea
3:49:08		210 ↓		NE of Univ.	Profile 1 ↓ from 210. Start Much higher neph than Profile 4. Water. Some neph issues. Lower visibility out window.
04:11:05					End Profile 1. Start Run 1. ^{name of} 200'.
04:21:40					Shallow misc ~ 200 feet. Dry land haze (dew)
04:21:40					End Run 1. Climb to 500 feet.
4:22:31					Start Orbit 1
4:23:57					End Orbit 1
04:27:12					Profile 2. 800' down to 100'
04:28:11					Run 2 Start. 100'. Toward Land
04:34:54					End of Run 2. Entered land haze at end Clear & dustier than start of Run 2
					Profile 3 ↑ to 1000' ⁽⁵⁰⁰⁰⁾
04:41:30		1600 feet.			End of Profile 3. Start of Run 3. Cox was (sea to land)
					Neph ~ 25s. Not very bumpy
4:53:53		"			Old wet dirt plus? from below?
4:55:10		"			End of Run 3. Cox bumpy ahead.

4:56:33

Start of Profile 3 ↑ from 100' back SE track.

(Orig selected Plot)

A. P.P.P.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B 437** Date 23 April 09 Name JOHN MARSHAM Page 2 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
5:12					Mid tide on profile - sea breeze picking up dust on coast.
					Dust in land CSL. Clear above. Then eroded dust layer below substrate lid.
5:15:15					eroded dust layer conc ² increases towards coast.
5:14:23					End of Profile. 4 at FL240 (over sea towards)
5:25:42					Sound 1 on point A.
5:31:42					Sound 2 ~25 km from coast (Chute Valley).
32:10					Sound 3 ~15 km " " (" ").
5:34:30		FL240.			Coast sea to land
5:38:00		"	land	sea	Sound 4 ~30 km inland.
					Lider shows clear layer at bottom present in depth on this run. Deeper over land - not clear on ocean. Land CSL dust at very bottom. (Lider synch on 2 FL240 runs)
55:46:12					Sound 4 at B. Then around \
					Again eroded ^{elevated} dust thicker out at sea.
					Clear layer gets less deep out at sea.
06:05:12					End of run 5. Start orbit 2. Over sea.
06:08:18					Start Orbit 3.
06:11:00		FL240.			End orbit 3 Turn around at A Head to land.
06:13:39		FL240 to FL120	To land 311°		Start Profile 4 & towards FL120.
6		603 hPa			hazy dust layer. 13400' TKE (as we cross coast).
06:21:38		12000'			End Profile 4. Start Run 6 663 hPa.
06:36:46					R.P.P. at around B) End of run P.P.

33

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B** ⁴³⁷ Date 23 April 09 Name JOHN MARDON Page 3 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
06:38:30					Pable 5 start down from FL20 to FL50
06:45:59					End Pable 5 at 500', Pable 6 start up! No TMO at 500' (not yet used).
06:49:22					End Pable 6 ↑ 7.9 hkt. Turn back to land.
06:52:49	7	FL80	325		Start Run 7 at 8000', Towards land.
06:53:14					Sea → level. PP camp - Prew Vis decreased.
06:58:16					Bumps. Td detection?
07:06:32		FL80			End of Run 7 - Turn around. P.P.P.
07:08:11					Start Pable 7 ↓ from FL80 to Prew hPa darker than last time.
07:13:43					Jaw' 900 hPa 2400 P.P.P.
07:16:30					End of Pable 7 1400' (Turn) ^{P.P.P. some}
07:17:58			N 354°		Start Run 8 1500' Most phase on run ^{why?}
07:26:57					End of Run P. Heimn ≤ 15°C Pable up ↑
07:29:22					End of TKE ~ 760 hPa ^{w/ Lid 900 hPa} Dunk mixed to 300 hPa
07:40:36					TRE 21°N 58°36'E Mins?
? ~ 7:48					Level ↓ to hkt Muxet. P.P. etc. into
07:56:20					Level Muxet. Vis not worse than before. //?
					7:31 → 7:38 level.
					Phase ↓ hkt av 7:38 I think

Mult ↑ FL20

Flight B437 03:42:44

Heading 117 deg Speed 313 knots Height 21.0kft Press 445mb

Lat 23°0.0'N Long 59°18.0'E Wind 12 ms-1/ 298 deg

Temp -16.37C Dewpoint -49.56C

From 01:41:55 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	445.97	mb
++++	OZONE MIXING RATIO	41.54	ppb
....	NEPH BLUE SP	3.92	m-1

Flight B437 04:56:02

Heading 116 deg Speed 223 knots Height 1.4kft Press 960mb

Lat 22°0.0'N Long 58°36.0'E Wind 1 ms-1/ 37 deg

Temp 29.72C Dewpoint -12.25C

From 04:28:11 to now

Run 3.

Current values			
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	17760	secs
—	NONDEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	28.95	deg C
- - -	DEW POINT	-12.25	deg C

CA?

Current values			
.....	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	17769	secs
.....	NEPH BLUE SP	58.27	m-1
.....	NEPH GREEN SP	63.24	m-1
.....	NEPH RED SP	62.55	m-1

5.2 CA

B437#mevexViRClog.txt

```
*** Opened channel log for #MEVEX at 23/04/2009 06:12:31
[06:12] *** FAAMOpsDoug (~vircuser@85.154.2.208) has joined #MEVEX
[06:12] *** Mode change [+nt] on #MEVEX by photon.ge.phy.umist.ac.uk
[06:14] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.208) has joined #MEVEX
[06:23] *** FAAM (~GLUXE@203.38.13.7) has joined #MEVEX
[06:24] <FAAM> Hello from -146
[06:24] <FAAMOpsDetach> Hiya
[06:24] [FAAMOpsDoug] Hello from the Golden Tulip
[06:26] <FAAMOpsDetach> The Food and Beverage Manager apologises for the limited
        breakfast
[06:26] <FAAM> 20 30N 59 24E. SATCOM-C u/s
[06:27] <FAAMOpsDetach> Have you tried h_stop/start h_satcom + resetting the CB?
[06:28] <FAAM> yes... looks like a connection problem again... cannot see hardware
        status, for example
[06:30] <FAAMOpsDetach> okay
[06:31] <FAAM> some of the messagees are now queing, however
[06:31] <FAAMOpsDetach> is there one which is "issued"?
[06:32] <FAAM> yes...now no, it just changed to succesful
[06:34] <FAAMOpsDetach> okay, looks like its working now then.
[06:35] <FAAMOpsDetach> Nice
[06:53] <FAAM> FWVS is gttng data, except it looks like temp rather than dew pt!
[06:54] <FAAM> we've had no wx, can PC resend?
[06:59] <FAAM> cancel that last request - I can see the messages that didn't make it on
        the faam web page
[07:03] <FAAMOpsDetach> okay. I sent a test email, did that come through?
[07:07] <FAAM> nope
[07:08] <FAAMOpsDetach> are there still lots of items in the queue?
[07:09] <FAAM> weirds-ville
[07:10] <FAAMOpsDetach> meaning?
[07:10] <FAAM> there are no items queueing, I can see the turnaround message on the FAAM
        website, but nothing received at the aircraft
[07:18] <FAAM> hows the bevvvy sitch?
[07:18] <FAAMOpsDetach> none at all so far today!
[07:21] <FAAM> can The Food and Beverage Manager not supply some dairy?
[07:22] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.208) has quit IRC [Read error: Connection
        reset by peer]
[07:23] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.208) has joined #MEVEX
[07:25] <FAAM> off for some dairy?
[07:27] <FAAMOpsDetach> off to get a cuppa now
[07:42] <FAAMOpsDetach> ETA?
[07:54] <FAAM> 0750Z
[07:55] <FAAM> can u pass on to PC please?
[08:01] <FAAMOpsDetach> yip, Pete is here with me
[08:03] *** FAAM (~GLUXE@203.38.13.7) has left #MEVEX
[08:04] *** FAAM (~GLUXE@203.38.13.7) has joined #MEVEX
[08:09] <FAAM> camels on the port bow
[08:18] <FAAMOpsDetach> photos please
[08:18] <FAAMOpsDetach> Kitch and Steve aware of new eta
[08:20] <FAAM> new ET now 0800Z
[08:21] <FAAM> New ETA 0800Z
[08:22] <FAAM> can u confirm receipt?
[08:24] <FAAMOpsDetach> msg sent to ops 'n engs
[08:28] <FAAMOpsDetach> did the big dust get lifted?
[08:42] <FAAMOpsDetach> offf to the airport
[08:42] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.208) has left #MEVEX
[09:03] *** FAAM (~
```

Cloud Physics Flight Log B437

Date:	Operator:	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	AUX1 Time:	AUX2 Time:
-------	-----------	-----------	------------	------------	------------	------------

DAU2 Disk space? 1.6GB

	PCASP SPP-200		CDP		PCASP		2DC		FFSSP		SID3	
Operated?	y		y		y		y		y		N	
Pre-flight checks	Vref	7.3	Ref V (~3):	3.5	Vref (>7):	N/S	El#1 V (>1):	1.1	Ref V:	3.6	Comms?	
	Sample flow	1.35			Flow (~1):	.72	El#32 V (>1):	1.3				
	Sheath flow	16.5			Pressure:	1009						
					Temp (NDIT)	28.8C						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
													2DC cleaned
													PCASPs both run with no heaters due to high external temperatures
													SID 3 would not connect
													The network Autonegotiated at 100Mb/s Even though we know it can only support 10 Mb/s. It also caused the Horace Connection to fail.
													Tried forcing to 10 Mb/s, both full and half Duplex and unplugging Horace network.
													None of these helped.
	010	1		2000		2000							
03:23:45	020	0		80		40							Left boundary layer
03:39:00													Spike in SPP200 to 30000, possible ch1 noise, but then fell back to ~100
03:44:00													Switched all heaters on
03:45:00	210												Ch1 noise on pcase 100X, possibly some on pcase spp200 also
03:49:10	210	0		100		2000					2		
03:54:10	160	0		200	0.1	5000	0.06				2		

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
03:56:00	140	0		500	1.8	800	0.07				2		Reentered boundary layer, noise on PCASPs reduced
03:58:10	120	0.4		700	2	100	0.09				2		
04:02:00	080	0.4		10000	1.7	300	0.11						Massive difference between PCASPs. This is not ch1 noise, the spectrum on SPP200 looks sensible.
04:07:20	040	0.4		7000	2	600	0.1						
04:11:45	018	0.4		8000	1.5	600	0.1				6		
04:15:00	250 ft	0.2		3000	2.8	600	0.09				7		End profile 1 start run 1
04:18:30	250 ft	0.3		570	2	600	0.09				7		
04:22:00	250 ft	0.25		520	1.9	530	0.09				8		End run 1
													Orbit
													Profile 2 down to 100 ft
04:28:10	100ft	0.25		600	0.5	700	0.09				9		Start run 2
04:32:10													Turned off heaters
04:36:00	100 ft	0.5		400	1	400	0.1				11		
04:40:00	100 ft	0.6		400	1.7	400	0.1				12		End run 2
04:41:30	015	0		100	1	100	0.1				12		Start run 3
04:55:00	015	0		200	2	200	0.1				13		More variability in pcasps End run 3
													Start profile 3
04:59:30	040	0		50		70	0.09				13		
05:02:40	075	0.4		450	0.4	450	0.11				13		
05:05:00	100	0.4		400	0.4	400	0.11				13		
05:08:00													restarted SPP200 pcasp to see if it would clear excessively large MVD values – seems to now be giving sensible values
05:13:00	180	0		2000	0.1	10	0.07				14		
05:18:00													Turned on heaters
05:24:00	240	0		200	0.1	4000	0.05				14		Ch1 noise on both PCASPs
06:24:36	130	0.4		20000		400							Pcasp 100 x seems to have recovered but still seeing noise spikes
06:25:40	120	0.3		20000		300	0.11				16		Start run 6
06:29:00	120	0.4		20000		300	0.12				16		Fully recovered on pcasp 100X

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics	Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (old)	Vref:	
	Flow:	
2DC	EI#1:	
	EI#32:	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	
	Flow:	
CDP	Laser V:	
FFSSP	Ref V:	
SID 3	Laser V:	
Rack Equipment		Please note SEADAS disk space remaining.

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B437

Date:

23-04-2009

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)	Bottom inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)
-----------------------------------	------------------	------------------------------------	---------------------	------------------------------------

Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	B437-N8	----	----	Bottom					Blanks Thrown (because torn during the sampling)
Filters run1	B437-N9	----	----	Top					
Filters run 2	B437-N10	----	----	Bottom					Blanks
Filters run 2	B437-N11	----	----	Top					
Filters run 3	B437-N12	----	----	Bottom	06:26:17	06:36:42		349	V _{bottom} > V _{top} V = pumped air volume
Filters run 3	B437-N13	----	----	Top	06:26:17	06:36:42		252	
Filters run 4	B437-N14	----	----	Bottom	06:53:31	07:04:06		415	
Filters run 4	B437-N15	----	----	Top	06:53:31	07:04:06		322	

Flight:

B437

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:
 Heimann:
 Deiced Temp:
 Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:
 Buck CR2:
 General Eastern:
 Johnson Williams:
 Nevzorov:
 Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:
 Forward Facing:
 Rearward Facing:
 Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:
 GIN Applanix:
 INU Honeywell:
 Radar Altimeter:
 RVSM IAS:
 RVSM Static Pressure:
 XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:
 AMTG:
 AVAPS:
 Cabin Pressure:
 Printer:
 S9 Static Pressure:
 Satcom C:
 Satcom H (VIRC):
 Turb Centre-Static:
 Turb Left Right:
 Turb Up-Down:
 Turb Horizontal Chk:
 Turb Vertical Chk:
 Weather Radar:
DLUs:
 DLU AERACK:
 DLU BBR Lower:
 DLU BBR Upper:
 DLU Core Chem:
 DLU Core Consoles:
 DLU Port Aft:
 DLU Port Fwd:
 DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:
 BBR (clear) Lower:
 BBR (IR) Lower:
 BBR (red) Lower:
Upper:
 BBR (clear) Upper:
 BBR (IR) Upper:
 BBR (red) Upper:
 ARIES:
 DEIMOS:
 IR Camera:
 JNO2 Lower:
 JNO2 Upper:
 JO1D Lower:
 JO1D Upper:
 MARSS:
 SHIMS Lower:
 SHIMS Upper:
 SWS:
 TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:
 2DP:
 FFSSP:
 PCASP:
 PCASP SPP-200:
 2DS:
 ADA:
 CAPS:
 CCN:
 CDP (fuselage):
 CDP (Canister):
 CIP 100 (PIP):
 CIP 25 (CIP):
 CPI:
 CVI (Inlet):
 CVI PCASP-X:
 CVI Ly-A Hygro:
 FSSP (UMan):
 SID1:
 SID2:
 SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:
 CPC 3786 H2O:
 Filters 47mm:
 Filters 90mm:
 Neph - Dry:
 Neph - Wet:
 PSAP:
 AMS:
 CPC (AMS):
 SMPS (AMS):
 CPC 3010A (CVI):
 INC:
 Mini-LIDAR:
 SP2:
 UHSAS:
 VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:
 NOx TE42C:
 Ozone TE49C:
 Ozone TE49:
 SO2 TE43C:
 TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
 TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
 FAGE:
 Formaldehyde:
 NOx FAAM:
 NOxy:
 ORAC:
 PAN:
 PERCA:
 Peroxide:
 PTRMS:
 TDLAS (1C):
 WAS Bags:
 WAS Bottles:
Misc Non-Core
 CASI/ATM:
 LIDAR (big):
 LTI:
 SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B437

Date: 23rd April 2009

Instruments

SID3 failed to operate

IR camera: short-wave camera continues not to be functional

CVI – no HORACE input. Hygrometer not used.

PCASP (new) – sensible spectra but concentrations factor of 10 too high

FWVS – connection to HORACE suspect.

SATCOM-H: failed to receive any messages. Problems connecting to SATCOM to get status information.

GIN – failed to lock on to correct position at the start of the flight. After 20 mins airborne, locked on ok.

AMTG screen blanked towards end of flight.

CPC – failed to operate correctly during flight and recorded no data.

SWS – modules ceased communications on several occasions during flight

Drosondes – three from five dropped had no parachute

ARIES – some dropouts: thermal problems suspected

Lower pyrgeometer – data suspect

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

none

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 23/4/09

Flight No: B 437

Pre-Flighter: Doug A

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	✓	Hangar	Collect spanners	Core Chem - 9/16" & 11/16"
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	WATE DONE	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	✓	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	WATE	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	WATE	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	✓	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	✓	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
10	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	✓	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	No ILO = OK HOW LOG ADJUSTED
12	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	✓	Nevezorov	Checked and OFF	
14	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	✓	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	WATE DONE	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
17	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	✓	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	✓	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	✓	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	✓	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	✓	Satcom C	Checked	
23	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
24	n/a	CNC	Butanol filled	
25	n/a	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
26	n/a	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	NOT ILO
27	n/a	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
28	✓	3876 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
29	n/a	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	
30	n/a	CCN SS cols A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	
31	n/a	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	
32	n/a	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	
33	✓	3786 CPC	Drained	
34	✓	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	
<u>External Checks</u>				
35	✓	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
36	✓	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
37	✓	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
38	✓	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
39	✓	Nevezorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
40	✓	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
41	✓	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	CLEAR BARRER SCATTERED / NOT USED
42	✓	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
43	✓	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
44	✓	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
45	✓	All other covers	Removed	
46	✓	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
47	✓	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
48	✓	Tools	Avalon informed	
49				
50				
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
51	✓	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
52	✓	ICEX applied		
53	✓	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more

ARIES flight log

Flight: B437

page 1 of 2

Date: 23 APR 09

Operator(s): S. Rogers

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: MEVEX; South + east of Muscat

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
02 40 58	Power up	OK					
02 58 15	—	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal window 33 mirror 23.
03 10 00	—	cal	CH	0	82	41	CH cal.
03 11 55	—	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal
03 23 30		Z	Z	0	81	41	free run Z for filmvette
03 18 —		cal	CH	0			CH cal
03 40 01	FL210	Z 1 min	Z	0	81	42	Z 1 min macro
03 41 52		N 3 min	N	0	81	41	N 3 min
04 15 29		Z 3 min	Z	0	81	42	Z 3 min
04 18 26	250ft	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadr - after Heiman cal. window: 32C
04 20 04		Z 3 min	Z	0	81	42	Z 3 min mirror: 33C
04 22 38	01 50ft						G 45°
04 26 49							Skid sampling - repositioning.
04 28 11	R2 100ft		Z	0	81	41	—
04 30 00	100ft	240x1	N	0	81	42	Nadr - after Heiman cal.
04 32 05	"	Z 3 min	Z	0	81	42	Z 3 min
04 39 07	"	N 3 min	N	0	81	42	N 3 min climb to 1500ft as we approach the coast.
04 41 34			N				Coast crossing. Descent below
04 49 01		240x1	Z	0	81	43	#Z CBB flocky at ambient?
04 50 43		N 3 min	N	0	81	44	N 3 min window 36 mirror 36 End 04 56
05 16 26	FL210	Z 3 min					
05 19 01	FL240	Z 3 min	Z	0	81	41	Z 3 min (first and only Z starts during maneuvers)
		N 3 min	N	0			↳ Hm. Something odd. 3 mins of CBB?
05 24 21	"	Z 1 min	Z	0	81	41	Z 1 min Sound 05:25
05 26 —	"	N 3 min	N	0	81	41	N 3 min - poss. crossing coast during cal.
05 36 —	"	Z 3 min	Z	0	81	41	Z 3 min aborted
							↳ Hm. Something odd - 3 mins of CBB
05 38 05	"	Z 1 min	Z	0	81	41	Z 1 min
05 40 13	"	N 3 min	N	0	81	41	N 3 min window 24 mirror -1
05 47 38		Z 3 min	Z	0	81	41	Z 3 min
05 50 27		N 3 min	N	0	82	42	N 3 min over desert

ARIES flight log

Flight: B 437

page 2 of 2

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
055559	FL240		N				Crossed coast, but was cal ended in time?
06 01 40		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
06 03 05		240x1	N	0	81	41	N
06 04 32		240x1	Z	0	81	41	Z
06 06 32	02	240x1	N	0	81	41	N in orbit 30° bank Orbit abandoned
06 08 34	03	240x1	N	0	81	41	N — " —
06 10 37		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal. Before orbit completed.
06 25 48	FL120	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
06 27 08		240x1	Z	0	81	41	Z (stopped half way to sync with SWS)
06 28 04		240x1	N	0	81	41	N
06 30 11		240x1	Z	0	81	41	Z
06 31 48		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
06 33 06		240x1	N	0	81	41	N Window 19C Mirror 10C
06 35 04		240x1	Z	0	81	41	Z
36 51		240x1	N	0			N
06 36 52		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
06 41 06		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
06 43 00							"Unable to get instrument status" Restarting
06 46 -							"Unable to open board" Connection but "Speed = 1304 scans/sec"
06 57 23		cal	CH	0	58	36	CH cal } ignore! targets not yet stable
06 58 37		240x1	Z	0	55		Z
07 06 43		cal	CH	0	81	34	CH cal
07 14 05		cal	CH	0	81	34	CH cal Window 25 Mirror 28
07 15 57		cal	CH	0	81	34	CH cal.
07 17 57	1500 Ph.	240x1	Z	0	81	35	Z 1013
		N3run	N	0	81	36	N3run
07 25 35		240x1	Z	0	81	39	Z
07 27		cal	CH	0	81	39	CH cal.

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	23/04/09	Flight	B437	log pages
Operator(s)	J Bowles	Campaign	MEVEX			
Departure	MUSCAT	Arrival	MUSCAT			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						Y	
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•	
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•	
FERA on	at time				01:28		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	35°C	Ch 17	35°C	Ch18	30°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on	at time				01:29↓		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	299	Cold	290			
Target heating						•	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•	
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time						
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual		•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor				Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	03:13:10		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.6	Cold	302.7	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16 (40-44)	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)	Ch20 (44-48)	
	38.6	31.0	39.9	41.0	42.1	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again					at time	

Double 'Dry' Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B 437**.....

 Date **23/04/09**.....

 Operator's name: **A. Wilson**.....

 Page **1** of **3**.....

GMT	Run	Height	Cyclone On?	Inlet RH	Dry neph flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph flow	Wet neph RH	Remarks
030000Z			WET						GOOD PREFLIGHT - BOTH NEPHS ZERO'D OK.
034800	TRANSIT	FL 210			13		13		Clear air mass today. Little dust. Both Neph's good!
034909	P1	FL 210			13		13		Start P1 @ 100ft.
035530	P1	FL 130			14		14		Big increase in Dry Neph. No change in Wet Neph.
040430	P1	500ft			17		17.0		Wet Neph now increasing.
040900	"	3200		17.6	15	19.7	15.7	16.5	Adjust flows.
041506	P1/R1	250ft		77	15	64	14.1	69	end P1 & Start R1 @ 250ft.
041725	"	"		86	15	100	20	81	adjust cyclone flow beyond cut off!
042140	R1								end R1
042231	orbit 1	500ft		76	15	90.5	20	73.2	Start orbit 1. 45° Left turn.
042356									end orbit 1.
042713	P2	500ft		81	15	81	20	76.5	Start P1 @ 100ft.
042811	R2	100ft		87.6	15	100	20	85	Start R2
043200	"	"		91.1	15	100	14.1	89.3	adjust cyclone below cut off.
	R2/P3	100ft		27	15	63	13.9	45	end R2 start P3 @ 1500ft. Crossing coast
044134	P3/P3	1500ft		7	15	18	13.4	19	end P3 start P3
044530	R3	1500ft		6	15	10	20	12	
044600	"	"					6.5		trying to establish cyclone cut flow @ 1500ft.
044830	"	"					9.1		Cyclone cutting. outside pressure 960mb.

Double 'Dry' Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B** 437

Date 23/4/09

Operator's name: A. Wilson

Page 2 of 3

GMT	Run	Height	Cyclone On?	Inlet RH	Dry neph flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph flow	Wet neph RH	Remarks
045510	R3	1500ft	Wet	8	14	7	12.7	9	end R3. outside air pressure (OAP) 960mb.
-"-	R3 →								Start R4 @ FL240
051973	R3	FL240			12		8.8		end R3 @ 26000ft
052530	R4	"							start R4
054639	"	-"-			12		8.8		end R4
054807	R5	FL240		0	12	0	8.9	0	Start R5
060553	"			0		0		0	end R5
060619	orbit 2	-"-		0	12	0	8.8	0	Start orbit 3
060754	-"-								abandoned.
060818	orbit 3	-"-			12		9.3		Start orbit 3.
061350	"	-"-			"		"		end orbit 3
061350	R4	FL240			13		10.1		Start R4 to FL120
062538		FL120			15		13.2		
062549	R6	-"-			15		13.2		start R6 - DRY NEPH increasing. Wet NOT. Why?
063643	R6	-"-		11	15	8	13.3	9.9	end R6.
063832	R5	FL120		11.3	14	8.3	13.4	10.1	Start R5
									WET NEPH started to pick up at FL60 (840mb OAP)
									before profile descent was reversed. Now heading
									back to ~ 8000ft.
064555									end R5 @ 5000ft

Double 'Dry' Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B** 437

Date 23/4/09

Operator's name: A. Wilson

Page 3 of 3

GMT	Run	Height	Cyclone On?	Inlet RH	Dry neph flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph flow	Wet neph RH	Remarks
065254	R7	F080	WET	14	15	13.8	20	13	START R7
065540							9.7		adjust cyclone flow
070624	R7								end R7
070811	R8	F080		8	13	5	9.8	11	start R8
071500		2500ft		7	14	4	11.8	8	WET WDH Good @ 925mb static pressure (2500ft)
071641	R8	1500ft		7	14	3	12	6	end R8 bumpy.
071801	R8	1500ft							start R8
071945		-"-					20		adjust cyclone flow beyond cut off
		-"-							wet neph counts dropped by approx 20%.
072303		-"-			15		9.8		cyclone flow adjust. counts jump up 6!
072555		-"-					20		cyclone adjust. counts drop. Good.
	R8	1500ft							end run 8. climbing for transit back to muscat.
	TRANSIT	F120							

Impactor performance

17 → 10 → 22 - 15 → 25
 on off on off

ALS450 LIDAR FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT NUMBER:

B437

OPERATOR:

Joss

DATE:

23/04/09

WATER FILL:

No + top up.

Campaign:

NEVER

WATER EMPTY:

No

Ct:

359.045

Cw:

359.045

930 - 1000
20'

Run No:	Altitude	Start Time	Stop Time	Int. Time	Head Temp	Water Temp	Notes	
Transition		0329	0337	100/5	32	37.5	Profile up. 4 E3 0-0. These values are good for boundary layer dust.	
Transition	FL2	033930	035739	1200/60	32	37.5		
P1	P1	035805	041509	200/10	29	37.5		
end P2	1500'	0440	044600	20/1				
P3	1200'?	044630	0455	100/5	29	37.8		
P3		045635	050230	100/5	30			
P3		050350	0517	200/10				
P4	FL240	051845	052604	400/20				
P4	FL240	052640		1200/60			Clear layer increasing in Alt as we head inland	
P4	FL240	0543	060619	1200/60			Dust layer seems to be reducing in thickness from below	
		0600 - layer gets thicker & higher as we go over the sea						
P3	P4	intensity of image gradually increasing over the two runs. The structure is the same but has increased in intensity						
P4	FL240	061358	063643	200/10			Included run @ FL120	
	FL120	0626		200/10				
ops		063856	0650	200/10				
P7	FL80	065045	071659	100/5			Run over coast.	
		covering in @ 065353					Profile 1156 dust seen in	
		5 sec is a good in-gate boundary layer was						
		071400	Dust layer just going into					
P8	1500			150/5	20/1	22	37.8	Keeping on in profile.
Transition		073400						

As we come over mountains, layer clears

Southern Asia CAM Aerosol Optical Depth
At 06Z on 23/04/2009, from 12Z on 21/04/2009

AOD T+042

Southern Asia CAM Aerosol Optical Depth
At 09Z on 23/04/2009, from 12Z on 21/04/2009

AOD T+045

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 09Z on 23/04/2009, from 12Z on 21/04/2009

Dust concentration (log1) T+045

22.51
55.53

METOP-A 2009/04/23 UTC

METOP-A ORBITAL PREDICT PLOT

EPOCH DATE: 09/01/28

■ lat: 22.667 lon: 55.2 res: 9 km

Southern Asia CAM Horizontal Winds
At 06Z on 23/04/2009, from 12Z on 21/04/2009

Meridional Wind (leg1) T+042

Southern Asia CAM Horizontal Winds
At 06Z on 23/04/2009, from 12Z on 21/04/2009

Zonal Wind (leg1) T+042

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 06Z on 23/04/2009, from 12Z on 21/04/2009

Dust concentration (log1) T+042

Flight B437 03:38:02

Heading 71 deg Speed 306 knots Height 20.2kft Press 460mb

Lat 25°30.0'N Long 60°12.0'E Wind 1093 ms-1/ 229 deg

Temp -14.29C Dewpoint -43.33C

From start to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	460.35	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-14.29	deg C
-----	DEW POINT	-43.34	deg C

Profile 4
B (land) to A (sea)

Flight B437 05:20:19

Heading 234 deg Speed 311 knots Height 24.0kft Press 392mb

Lat 20°18.0'N Long 59°30.0'E Wind 29 ms-1/ 280 deg

Temp -18.39C Dewpoint -47.42C

From 04:56:33 to now

Current values		
-----	STATIC PRESSURE	392.28 mb
-----	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-18.39 deg C
-----	DEW POINT	-47.42 deg C